

THE PERCEPTION OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *Simultaneous translation is a type of oral translation, which involves the almost simultaneous reproduction of the translated passage with the perception of the speaker's speech. Typically, simultaneous interpretation takes place in a booth, and listeners receive the interpreter's speech through headphones. Simultaneous translation involves the skill of simultaneous perception in the source language and reproduction in the target language while maintaining the pace of the speaker's speech.*

Key words: *memory, definition, semantic discourse, segmentation, consecutive, simultaneous, source language.*

Simultaneous translation involves hard work of memory, the ability to concentrate, make instant decisions, make predictions regarding the further development of an utterance, perform speech compression if necessary, etc.

While many interpreters do both consecutive and simultaneous interpreting, the English term 'conference interpreter' usually refers only to simultaneous interpreters. Conferences, as an event, can be defined as discursive transactions during which experts gather to strategize progress on key issues. The concept of "transaction" in the above definition enables us to consider interpretation as an interaction phenomenon.

Simultaneous translation is a special type of professional interlingual activity carried out in extreme linguistic and psychological conditions, in an environment hostile to the simultaneous interpreter. Certain conditions are necessary for the success of this activity. First of all, it is the objective semantic discourse redundancy of the message in the source language and its subjective semantic redundancy for the

translator. And if the first follows from the repetition and interdependence of discourse components at all levels of speech (syllable, word, phrase, syntagm, utterance, discourse, communicative situation), then the latter - the subjective redundancy of the message - requires certain conclusions (cognitive, pragmatic, contextual, situational) [Chernov, Setton, Hild 2004: 200].

“The act of simultaneous translation can be considered as an act of complex speech communication, as a speech operation, which is a link inserted into the break in the communication chain from the speaker to the listener, provided that the first and second speak different languages” [Chernov, Setton, Hild 2004: 200]. The translator must have an instant reaction to get used to the image of the speaker, while maintaining the skill of automatic segmentation of the sentence and the distribution of its components, which is an intuitive analysis of speech.

The need for simultaneous perception of the original and reproduction of the translation predetermines other characteristic features of simultaneous translation. First of all, among them one can single out a rigid time frame corresponding to the duration of the speaker's speech. To interpret the same speech in consecutive interpreting mode, the interpreter has twice as much time at his disposal as in simultaneous interpreting mode. Compared to written translation, this difference can be twenty or even thirtyfold. In addition to tight time limits, there is also a factor in the pace of the speech delivery by the speaker, which the interpreter must comply with. Simultaneous translation is characterized by the “segment-by-segment nature” of its implementation, that is, the implementation of translation in parts (segments) as they arrive, in contrast to consecutive and / or written translation, where it is possible to familiarize yourself with the text or its fragment in its entirety [Shiryaev 1979: 6 -7].

The simultaneous interpreter is busy simultaneously performing the following actions: 1) listening to information spoken by the speaker, that is, receiving a message; 2) understanding the meaning, that is, decoding the message; 3) converting the value into the target language, i.e. encoding the message; 4) voicing the translated version,

that is, the release of the message. Each of these actions has a complex hierarchical structure. All of them are produced in real time, taking into account the lack of time.

A.F. Shiryaev distinguishes three phases of simultaneous translation. Prior to the start of translation, based on his knowledge, the translator builds a “probabilistic model of oratory”, which is tested with the start of the actual speech of the speaker. Provided that the “presetting” of the translator was adequate, he can choose the right solution from those already prepared. If a mistake was made in the presetting, then the search for a solution is carried out on the basis of experience, knowledge and reference points highlighted in the translation. The first phase ends after the decision has been made. The second phase, or "implementation phase", involves the completion of the translation based on the chosen model. The last phase is the "control phase", during which the correctness of the translation is evaluated. The first two phases are characterized by transience, while the last one can be "stretched out in time" [Shiryaev 1979: 17-18]. It is also worth noting that the perception of the text should be carried out at the communicative level using a critical assessment of what was heard.

Simultaneous translation is characterized by a high degree of entropy, which can be caused by external (technical) factors and internal (personal) factors. A translator often encounters a situation where, for some reason, he cannot perceive or convey certain units, and is forced to compensate for this with the means at his disposal.

Simultaneous interpreters first master consecutive translation of both short segments and long speeches. During the consecutive translation of small fragments, the translator relies on memory and mentally divides each passage into several short ones, and during the consecutive translation of a long segment, he makes notes to simplify the further reproduction of what was said. During the training of interpreters, an integrated approach to teaching consecutive and simultaneous interpreting is very important, with the subsequent transition from the first type, where the interpreter learns accuracy and completeness of reproduction, to the second, where a high level of concentration is required to acquire the skill of simultaneous listening and speaking.

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